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Direct Infusion Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study			
Fish Oil Enriched Parenteral Nutrition Modulates Circulating Lipid Profiles in Intestinal Failure: A Lipidomics Approach of a Pilot Randomized Double-Blind Trial			
Document creation date	04/06/2026	Principal investigator	Natalia Vázquez Manjarrez
Institution	Instituto Nacional de Ciencias Médicas y nutrición Salvador Zubirán	Corresponding Email	natalia.vazquezm@incmnsz.mx
Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Targeted	Clinical	Yes

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	pH adjustment	None
2-phase system	2-step extraction	Special conditions	Lipids were extracted using a modified Bligh and Dyer biphasic protocol employing dichloromethane (DCM), methanol, and water. Samples were first brought into a monophasic mixture to enable efficient lipid solubilization, followed by induction of phase separation to isolate the organic (DCM) fraction containing lipids.
Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes		

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium acetate	Detector	Mass spectrometer
MS type	QTrap	MS vendor	SCIEX
Direct type	FIA	MS Level	MS ²
Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	0.7	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ²	Low resolution
Resolution at MS ²	Low	Recording mode of raw data at MS ²	Centroid mode
Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	Yes		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Type of Blanks	Solvent blank
Quality control	No		

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	No
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Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	No	Are metadata available?	Available on request
Raw data upload	Available on request		

Sample Descriptions

Lipidomics-20250620 / Human / Serum

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze, Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles, Preservation method
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Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	60	Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C
Instant sample preparation	No	Time to freeze	75
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Storage temperature	-80 °C
Storage time (month)	72	Freeze-thaw cycles	0
Additives	None		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) FA[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	FA	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M-H] ⁻
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
Fatty acyl carboxylate anions			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Additional dimension/techniques	DMS
How was/were the additional dimension(s) used?	For separation of isobaric/isomeric interference	Was a model used to predict lipid molecule separation?	No
Lipid Identification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics Assiatant v1.5/ Data Analyst Sciex	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A	Further identification remarks	Detected in negative mode as pseudo-MRM transitions with Q1 equal to Q3.

1) FA[M-H]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
dFA 18:1	290.3 > 290.3	FA	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics ASsitant (SLA)v1.5
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transition 290.3 > 290.3; M2 (no DMS), NEG.

2) PC[M+CH3COO]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+CH3COO] ⁻

Fragments for identification

Fragment name
FA2(+O)
FA1(+O)

Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Additional dimension/techniques	DMS
How was/were the additional dimension(s) used?	For separation of isomeric/isobaric compounds	Was a model used to predict lipid molecule separation?	No
Lipid Identification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics Assistant (SLA) v1.5 / Analyst	Data manipulation	Centroiding
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Further identification remarks	PC species were measured in negative mode as acetate adducts and identified using acyl anion fragments plus DMS separation.		

2) PC[M+CH₃COO]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
dPC 17:0_14:1	FA1(+O)		
dPC 17:0_16:1	FA1(+O)		
dPC 17:0_18:1	FA1(+O)		
dPC 17:0_20:3	FA1(+O)		
dPC 17:0_22:4	FA1(+O)		
dPC 17:0_14:1_	FA2(+O)		
dPC 17:0_16:1_	FA2(+O)		
dPC 17:0_18:1_	FA2(+O)		
dPC 17:0_20:3_	FA2(+O)		
dPC 17:0_22:4_	FA2(+O)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics Assistant (SLA v1.5)
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transition 781.6 > 225.2; M1 (DMS), NEG.

3) PG[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PG	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M-H] ⁻
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			

FA1(+O)

FA2(+O)

Isotope correction at MS ²	No	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Additional dimension/techniques	DMS
How was/were the additional dimension(s) used?	For separation of isomeric/isobaric compounds	Was a model used to predict lipid molecule separation?	No
Lipid Identification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics Assistant (SLA) v1.5 / Analyst	Data manipulation	Centroiding
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Further identification remarks	Negative-mode MRM transitions track acyl anion fragments.		

3) PG[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
dPG 17:0_14:1	FA1(+O)		
dPG 17:0_16:1	FA1(+O)		
dPG 17:0_18:1	FA1(+O)		
dPG 17:0_20:3	FA1(+O)		
dPG 17:0_22:4	FA1(+O)		
dPG 17:0_14:1_	FA2(+O)		
dPG 17:0_16:1_	FA2(+O)		
dPG 17:0_18:1_	FA2(+O)		
dPG 17:0_20:3_	FA2(+O)		
dPG 17:0_22:4_	FA2(+O)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics Assistant (SLA v1.5)
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transition 710.5 > 225.2; M1 (DMS), NEG.

4) PE[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
FA1(+O)			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	MS ² verified by standard	Yes

Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Additional dimension/techniques	DMS
How was/were the additional dimension(s) used?	For separation of isomeric/isobaric compounds	Was a model used to predict lipid molecule separation?	No
Lipid Identification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics Assistant (SLA) v1.3 / Analyst	Data manipulation	Centroiding
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Further identification remarks	Negative-mode MRM transitions track acyl anion fragments		

4) PE[M-H]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
dPE 17:0_14:1	FA1(+O)		
dPE 17:0_16:1	FA1(+O)		
dPE 17:0_18:1	FA1(+O)		
dPE 17:0_20:3	FA1(+O)		
dPE 17:0_22:4	FA1(+O)		
dPE 17:0_14:1_	FA2(+O)		
dPE 17:0_16:1_	FA2(+O)		
dPE 17:0_18:1_	FA2(+O)		
dPE 17:0_20:3_	FA2(+O)		
dPE 17:0_22:4_	FA2(+O)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics Assistant (SLA v1.5)
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transition 679.5 > 225.2; M1 (DMS), NEG.

5) PI[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PI	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M-H] ⁻
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
FA1(+O)			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Additional dimension/techniques	DMS
How was/were the additional dimension(s) used?	For separation of isomeric/isobaric compounds	Was a model used to predict lipid molecule separation?	No

Lipid Identification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics Assistant (SLA) v1.5 / Analyst	Data manipulation	Centroiding
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Further identification remarks	Negative-mode MRM transitions track acyl anion fragments.		

5) PI[M-H]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
dPI 17:0_14:1	FA1(+O)		
dPI 17:0_16:1	FA1(+O)		
dPI 17:0_18:1	FA1(+O)		
dPI 17:0_20:3	FA1(+O)		
dPI 17:0_22:4	FA1(+O)		
dPI 17:0_14:1_	FA2(+O)		
dPI 17:0_16:1_	FA2(+O)		
dPI 17:0_18:1_	FA2(+O)		
dPI 17:0_20:3_	FA2(+O)		
dPI 17:0_22:4_	FA2(+O)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics Assistant (SLA)v1.5
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transition 798.5 > 225.2; M1 (DMS), NEG.

6) PS[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PS	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M-H] ⁻
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
FA1(+O)			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Additional dimension/techniques	DMS
How was/were the additional dimension(s) used?	For separation of isomeric/isobaric compounds	Was a model used to predict lipid molecule separation?	No
Lipid Identification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics Assistant (SLA) v1.5 / Analyst	Data manipulation	Centroiding
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A

Further identification remarks Negative-mode MRM transitions track acyl anion fragments.

6) PS[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
dPS 17:0_14:1	FA1(+O)		
dPS 17:0_16:1	FA1(+O)		
dPS 17:0_18:1	FA1(+O)		
dPS 17:0_20:3	FA1(+O)		
dPS 17:0_22:4	FA1(+O)		
dPS 17:0_14:1_	FA2(+O)		
dPS 17:0_16:1_	FA2(+O)		
dPS 17:0_18:1_	FA2(+O)		
dPS 17:0_20:3_	FA2(+O)		
dPS 17:0_22:4_	FA2(+O)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics ASsitant (SLA)v1.5
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transition 723.5 > 225.2; M1 (DMS), NEG.

7) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SM	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+H] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name	HG(PC,184)		
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Additional dimension/techniques	DMS
How was/were the additional dimension(s) used?	For separation of isobaric/isomeric interference	Was a model used to predict lipid molecule separation?	No
Lipid Identification Software	SLA v 1.5 /Analyst	Data manipulation	Centroiding
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A

7) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	

dSM d18:1/16:1	HG(PC,184)
dSM d18:1/18:1	HG(PC,184)
dSM d18:1/20:1	HG(PC,184)
dSM d18:1/22:1	HG(PC,184)
dSM d18:1/24:1	HG(PC,184)

Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics ASsitant (SLA)v1.5
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transition 710.6 > 193.2; M1 (DMS), POS.

8) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+NH4] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
-FA1(+HO)-(NH3)			
-FA2(+HO)-(NH3)			
-FA3(+HO)-(NH3)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	SLA v1.5 / Data Analyst
Data manipulation	Centroiding	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A	Further identification remarks	MRM IDs in the method file are encoded as sum composition plus lost fatty acid, e.g. TG 52:3-FA16:0.

8) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
14:0-13:0-14:0 TG-d5	-FA1(+HO)-(NH3)		
14:0-15:1-14:0 TG-d5	-FA1(+HO)-(NH3)		
14:0-17:1-14:0 TG-d5	-FA1(+HO)-(NH3)		
16:0-15:1-16:0 TG-d5	-FA1(+HO)-(NH3)		
16:0-17:1-16:0 TG-d5	-FA1(+HO)-(NH3)		
16:0-19:2-16:0 TG-d5	-FA1(+HO)-(NH3)		
18:1-17:1-18:1 TG-d5	-FA1(+HO)-(NH3)		
18:1-19:2-18:1 TG-d5	-FA1(+HO)-(NH3)		

Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics ASsitant (SLA)v1.5
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transition 731.7 > 500.5; M2 (no DMS), POS.

9) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CE	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+NH4] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
FA1(+OH)-(NH3)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	SLA v1.5 / Analyst
Data manipulation	Centroiding	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A		

9) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
14:1 cholesteryl-d7 ester	FA1(+OH)-(NH3)		
16:1 cholesteryl-d7 ester	FA1(+OH)-(NH3)		
18:1 cholesteryl-d7 ester	FA1(+OH)-(NH3)		
20:3 cholesteryl-d7 ester	FA1(+OH)-(NH3)		
22:4 cholesteryl-d7 ester	FA1(+OH)-(NH3)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics ASsitant (SLA)v1.5
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transition e.g. 619.6 > 376.4; M2 (no DMS), POS.

10) DG[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	DG	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+H] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
-FA1(-H)-(H ₂ O+NH ₃)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	SLA v1.5 Data Analyst
Data manipulation	Centroiding	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A		

10) DG[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
17:0-14:1 DG-d5	-FA1(-H)-(H ₂ O+NH ₃)		
17:0-16:1 DG-d5	-FA1(-H)-(H ₂ O+NH ₃)		
17:0-18:1 DG-d5	-FA1(-H)-(H ₂ O+NH ₃)		
17:0-20:3 DG-d5	-FA1(-H)-(H ₂ O+NH ₃)		
17:0-22:4 DG-d5	-FA1(-H)-(H ₂ O+NH ₃)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics ASsitant (SLA)v1.5
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transition e.g. 575.5 > 332.2; M2 (no DMS), POS.

11) Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Cer	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+H] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
LCB(-HO)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	SLA v1.5 / Data Analyst
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A

11) Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
C16:1 Ceramide-d7 (d18:1-d7/16:1)	LCB(-HO)		
C18:1 Ceramide-d7 (d18:1-d7/18:1)	LCB(-HO)		
C20:1 Ceramide-d7 (d18:1-d7/20:1)	LCB(-HO)		
C22:1 Ceramide-d7 (d18:1-d7/22:1)	LCB(-HO)		
C24:1 Ceramide-d7 (d18:1-d7/24:1)	LCB(-HO)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics ASsitant (SLA)v1.5
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transition e.g. 543.5 > 271.4; M2 (no DMS), POS.

12) HexCer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	HexCer	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+H] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
LCB(-H3O2)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	SLA v1.5 / Analyst
Data manipulation	Centroiding	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A		

12) HexCer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
C15 Glucosyl(β) Ceramide-d7 (d18:1-d7/15:0)	LCB(-H3O2)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics ASsitant (SLA)v1.5
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transition 693.6 > 271.4; M2 (no DMS), POS.

13) LacCer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LacCer	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+H] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
LCB-(H3O2)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	SLA V1.5
Data manipulation	Centroiding	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A		

13) LacCer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
C15 Lactosyl(β) Ceramide-d7 (d18:1-d7/15:0)	LCB-(H3O2)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics ASsitant (SLA)v1.5
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transition 855.7 > 271.4; M2 (no DMS), POS.

14) PA[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PA	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+NH4] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No

Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	SLA V 1.5 / Analyst
Data manipulation	Centroiding	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A		

14) PA[M+NH₄]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
□ 15:0-18:1-d7-PA	[M+H] ⁻ -115		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics ASsitant (SLA)v1.5
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transition 685.5 > 570.5; M2 (no DMS), POS.

15) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+H] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
HG(PC,184)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	MS ² verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	SLA V1.5 / ANalyst
Data manipulation	Centroiding	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A		

15) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
dLPC 15:0	HG(PC,184)		
dLPC 17:0	HG(PC,184)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics ASsitant (SLA)v1.5

Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transition 487.3 > 184.1; M2 (no DMS), POS.
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16) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+H] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
-HG(PE,141)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	SLA V1.5/ Analyst
Data manipulation	Centroiding	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A		

16) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
17:0 Lyso PC-d5	-HG(PE,141)		
15:0 Lyso PE-d5	-HG(PE,141)		
17:0 Lyso PE-d5	-HG(PE,141)		
19:0 Lyso PE-d5	-HG(PE,141)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics ASsitant (SLA)v1.5
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transition 445.3 > 304.3; M2 (no DMS), POS.

17) LPI[M+NH₄]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPI	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+NH ₄] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			

-HG(PI,260)

Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	SLA V1.4 / Analyst
Data manipulation	Centroiding	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A		

17) LPI[M+NH₄]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
15:0 Lyso PI-d5	-HG(PI,260)		
17:0 Lyso PI-d5	-HG(PI,260)		
19:0 Lyso PI-d5	-HG(PI,260)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics ASsitant (SLA)v1.5
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transitione.g.581.3 > 304.3; M2 (no DMS), POS.

18) LPS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPS	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+H] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
FA1(+C3H5O2)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	SLA v1.5 / Analyst
Data manipulation	Centroiding	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A		

18) LPS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
15:0 Lyso PS-d5	FA1(+C3H5O2)		
17:0 Lyso PS-d5	FA1(+C3H5O2)		

Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics ASsitant (SLA)v1.5
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transition e.g. 489.3 > 304.3; M2 (no DMS), POS.

19) LPG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPG	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+NH4] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
-HG(PG,172)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	SLA v1.5
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A

19) LPG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
15:0 Lyso PG-d5	-HG(PG,172)		
17:0 Lyso PG-d5	-HG(PG,172)		
19:0 Lyso PG-d5	-HG(PG,172)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Shotgun Lipidomics ASsitant (SLA)v1.5
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Class-specific internal standard from method dictionary; representative ISTD transition 493.3 > 304.3; M2 (no DMS), POS.